

Research Article

Development of Specialized Underwater Drones for Man Overboard Situations on Oil and Gas Platforms

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Abstract: An oil platform is a large building outfitted with equipment for extracting petroleum and natural gas from submerged geological formations. The safety of the workers is of utmost importance since operating an oil rig is a risky industry. Explosions, equipment malfunctions, chemical exposure, and most importantly, falls are among the risks connected to oil rigs. By putting in place comprehensive safety protocols, personal protective equipment (PPE), and regular training, these hazards can be decreased. Emergency planning is essential to lowering the number of fatalities and injuries. Plans for evacuation and instruction in first aid are part of this. A safer workplace is also aided by technological advancements like automated systems and remote monitoring that lessen human exposure to dangerous situations. Our primary innovation is an underwater drone that can keep oil rig workers safe. This drone is only intended for use with a man overboard, or MOB. A name tag with a tracker and an application that the person in charge may utilise in the event of a MOB crisis is another invention that is fastened to the worker's overall. These innovations can support the growth and development of the offshore sector without endangering the lives of its employees.

Keywords: drone; oil rig; safety; technology; tracker.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A crew member or passenger who falls into the ocean and needs fast rescue is referred to as a "man overboard." Unexpected events, carelessness, or severe weather might cause someone to fall overboard. When a seafarer or offshore worker is in the middle of carrying out their duties on board a vessel, man-overboard mishaps frequently occur (Arnold & Itkin, 2024). One of the most dangerous

kinds of offshore incidents is a fall overboard. Depending on the state of the sea, it puts the crew member at urgent risk of hypothermia or drowning. Even though incidents of people falling overboard are uncommon, when they do happen, the person who falls is typically severely hurt by hitting items as they descend or even from hitting the water's surface. This is particularly valid in the event of an offshore installation fall.

According to Today and Today (2018), two offshore workers were injured on December 7, 2017, in an incident on the Aker BP-operated Tambar field offshore Norway. The incident took place on the Maersk Drilling-owned Maersk Interceptor jack-up rig. Aker BP confirmed a day later that one person passed away following the accident. The deceased, a Norwegian citizen and employee of Maersk Drilling, fell into the sea during maintenance work on the rig.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

In RescueWave, we have three products which are an underwater drone, a tracker, and a mobile application that are linked to each other. When an overboard situation happens, the application will be notified as soon as possible. Then via application, we can deploy the underwater drone. This drone will locate the victim by the tracker that is attached to the victim's uniform. The underwater drone will deploy a safety net to help secure and protect the victim. Moreover, nearby vessels or ships will also be notified about the location of the victim and possibly help them get into safety.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Benefits to The Community

3.1.1 GPS Tracker Device

Gain community assurance and trust in the safety sector by increasing confidence among the workers' families as well as in the local community. This will improve the general impression of the surrounding community about the oil and gas sector as a responsible employer for worker safety by installing the tracking system.

3.1.2 RescueWave Tracking Drone

RescueWave Tracking Drone serves as the first responder while waiting for another rescue, keeping the worker who fell into the water safe. In an emergency, its speedy deployment can greatly shorten reaction times, speeding up rescue operations and possibly saving lives.

3.1.3 Mobile Application

Having a mobile application as the link between the drone and tracker could potentially enhance safety measures for workers onboard. Furthermore, the RescueWave mobile application offers a range of data needed to ensure workers' safety on board conveniently and efficiently, including real-time location tracking provided by the tracker. If the tracker detects any workers are overboard, it will immediately transmit an alert alarm to notify the person in charge and activate the drone for assistance.

3.2 Potential Commercialization

3.2.1 GPS Tracker Device

The device can offer a subscription-based service for the accompanying application, providing ongoing access to real-time tracking data and analytics. This model can create a steady revenue stream for the business while ensuring continuous client support and updates. Next, adaptability to other industries because the GPS tracker technology can be adapted for use in other sectors, such as

construction, mining, and maritime operations. This versatility opens additional markets for commercialization, expanding the potential customer base.

3.2.2 RescueWave Tracking Drone

In rescue and search operations, time is the key. The effectiveness of the search operations may be affected by the cost and slowness of traditional methods like using boats or helicopters. On the other hand, search teams have a greater chance of finding people in crisis fast by covering vast areas much more swiftly with these advanced devices than they could with traditional methods.

3.2.3 Mobile Application

The mobile location-tracking application interconnects with smart drones and wearable trackers. It serves as a link between the drone and the tracker, providing first aid to locate the victim and assure their safety while waiting for rescue professionals to arrive. Emergency response teams most commonly use apps like NEON Personnel Tracker, Go Tenna Pro, and FirstNet. The majority of these apps help users by giving them data and device location, combining social networking, tracking, metering, and navigation (Frantz, 2020).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 GPS Tracker Device

This GPS tracker device, which also acts as a name tag will be attached to the outfit worn by the staff in oil and gas platforms and will be paired with the application we made so that we can get real-time information about the person who wears the tracker. This drone uses the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) network's trilateration method (Greg, 2023). This will allow search and rescue teams to determine the location by latitude and longitude of the person. This tracker will be attached to the outfit by Velcro. Velcro also is water resistant and needs a high amount of force to separate them. A two-inch strip, for instance, may support a person weighing up to 175 pounds (79.4 kg) (Stevens, 2021). This will ensure that the tracker will not be easily removed by the water current when MOB happens.

4.2 RescueWave Tracking Drone

In severe unwanted conditions of the ocean (Thunderstorms, heavy rain, rogue waves, etc), it can be nearly impossible to rescue operations using human energy and recover individuals who have fallen into the ocean. Taking this problem into account, we came up with the RescueWave Tracking Drone which is essential in search and rescue operations during harsh weather, minimizing human risks and low chances of saving lives as well as operating efficiently and smoothly under such extreme weather. Our RescueWave Tracking Drone, equipped with GPS and other remote sensing technologies can offer a more effective and safer alternative for search and rescue missions. Either rough situation or calm, the RescueWave Tracking Drone is provided with an attachable net designed to keep fallen individuals afloat until aid arrives. RescueWave Tracking Drone is constructed from a lightweight, flexible, and highly conductive material that ensures efficient operation in challenging marine environments. Not only RescueWave Tracking Drone corrosion-resistant, and durable when exposed to saltwater and our RescueWave Tracking Drone is built to withstand underwater pressure and impacts. These descriptions prove that our RescueWave Tracking Drone is nothing like a simple drone for its amazing durability in facing challenges and life-saving operations.

4.3 Mobile Application

The RescueWave mobile application is designed to enhance the safety of offshore workers by enabling authorities to monitor individuals during 'man overboard' (MOB) incidents. It has a variety of features such as a real-time GPS tracker, alarm alerts, pop-up notifications, and a direct emergency call function to notify nearby ships and responders for prompt assistance. The application offers various features, including check-in and check-out information to allow security personnel to share positions and guarantee everyone's safety, mass alarm notification to guarantee the person in charge is notified as soon as an incident or emergency occurs, an emergency call button that provides immediate assistance as soon as the tracker alarm goes off, the current location of the deployed drone and most importantly, an automated drone with an additional deploy button for quick deployment of our smart drone to locate workers' locations once tracking alarm detected.

4.4 Survey Results

Figures 1. Survey questions and responses from the participants about RescueWave Underwater Drone

We have conducted a survey regarding our product in which approximately 80% of respondents agreed that safety measures on oil and gas platforms are sufficient for all the staff. 44% of respondents voted 5 which is very helpful for our product and can be used to act as a first responder during Man Overboard situations. More than half of our respondents have heard about the Man Overboard (MOB) situation on oil and gas platforms. All our respondents agreed that safety measures on oil and gas platforms need to be improvised according to the latest technologies. Approximately 90% of respondents chose Yes to this question which drones can help in detecting and identifying the person involved in Man Overboard situations in oil and gas platforms.

5. CONCLUSION

To conclude, this invention is consistent with the Sustainable Development Goals established by the United Nations SDG 3: "Good health and well-being", SDG 13: Climate action", and SDG 14: "Life below water".

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